

Bridging gaps between rural and urban communities is key for progressing on biodiversity and preserving Europe's farms

Policy recommendations

To promote Farmer Clusters as an effective approach to improve biodiversity, environmental outcomes, and sustainability across farm landscapes the following policies are recommended:

- **Have all available incentive schemes carefully checked for consistency.** Farmers that are willing to change farm management practices based on incentive schemes notice quickly, when potential results counteract each other, or, if the conditions for the participation in an incentive scheme rule out the participation in another important activity.
- **Differentiate farms according to the economic level of risk they can take.** Farms with a stable income situation can afford taking more risks that are associated with changing management practices than farms that struggle economically. Farms with an unstable income situation need facilitation with strong economic elements first, while farms with a stable income situation can be included in facilitation with a focus on biodiversity from the beginning.
- **Reduce knowledge gaps in urban populations regarding farming methods and why they are used.** Farmers and citizens often view farming through different lenses, which often create distinct communication challenges (Regan and Kenny 2002, Tosun et al. 2024). These differing frames show up in policy priorities: urban residents tend to emphasise environmental/climate action and sustainable food production, while rural residents more often prioritise rural jobs and a fair standard of living for farmers. Yet climatic, technical, and financial limits mean change cannot happen overnight. Citizen Science events as they are organized by Farmer Clusters and/or open-door events for instance of lead farms contribute to a better understanding of the factors that farmers struggle with among the broad public. They are an excellent opportunity to pick up knowledge from rural communities, understand the presence of hard constraints such as low prices for fruit that cannot be sold as table fruit, the need of (permanent) vegetation cover on sloped fields for preventing erosion, digestibility of grass by ruminants compared with other livestock and many more and redirect effort toward changes that are achievable without unwanted side effects. As a policy-maker, consider joining events organized by Farmer Clusters or lead farms.

Transformative impact of Farmer Clusters on farmland biodiversity

The number of farms as well as farmland biodiversity is in decline in several regions of Europe, threatening both agroecosystem services and long-term food system resilience. While agri-environmental schemes (AES) aim to stabilize the situation, uptake and impact vary widely. Traditional top-down AES often fail to connect with farmers' local realities, values, and identity. In contrast, the Farmer Cluster approach offers a promising alternative. Farmer Clusters empower farmers to achieve their farming and environmental goals. By working together under the guidance of a skilled facilitator, farmers can tackle landscape-level restoration and have a greater impact than any one individual could accomplish alone. Using the bottom-up approach of the farmer clusters (McHugh et al. 2022), farmers identify their conservation priorities and choose which practices to implement collectively. This is an impactful way to address global issues such as biodiversity conservation at the landscape scale. As

well as the conservation benefits, Farmer Clusters can create support networks in rural communities, bridging gaps between policy-makers and farmers, and fostering both regional and national cohesion.

Approach and results

The **EU Horizon 2020 project FRAMEwork** explores the potential to replicate the Farmer Cluster model across Europe to enhance farmland biodiversity at a continental scale. The Born cluster in Luxembourg was initiated in 2020. Biodiversity-friendly practices introduced by the Farmer Cluster include pesticide-free fruit production, conservation of old and rare fruit cultivars by (re-)planting trees, extensive grazing and the installation of insect hotels, partly in collaboration with local residents. Leaning on experiences from the FRAMEwork project, this policy brief explains how the Born Farmer Cluster can play a role in promoting biodiversity, ecosystem services and sustainable farming practices; collaboration and knowledge exchange; and landscape-scale biodiversity monitoring.

Evidence of impact

By fostering collaboration among farmers within shared landscapes, Farmer Clusters serve as platforms for implementing sustainable practices, spurring innovation, and enhancing ecological resilience.

- **Identity change drives lasting behaviour**

Facilitated Farmer Clusters allow farmers to reimagine their role in biodiversity conservation. Through trust and peer exchange, they transition from isolated efforts to collaborative, nature-friendly practices. This shift in identity—from compliance to stewardship—encourages long-term behavioural change. In case of the Born cluster, the certification of the main stakeholder Ramborn as a B-Corp is evidence for the identity change.

- **Tangible ecosystem benefits and sustainable practices**

Farmer Clusters can deliver real environmental gains—from more stable pollination to biological pest control. Localised practices, such as extensive grazing, enhance soil life and retention as well as floral diversity.

- **Landscape-scale biodiversity monitoring and citizen science**

Camera traps operated by volunteer farmers of the Born Cluster revealed diverse wildlife at night within several interconnected orchards of the cluster area. Citizens were involved into biodiversity assessments during three issues of the City Nature Challenge, thereby sharing understanding of ecological changes across the landscape, building trust between farmers and the public, and fostering a sense of shared purpose. The positive impacts extended beyond biodiversity. In Born, the City Nature Challenge was organized along a walking trail to promote and sustain local recreational opportunities and cultural heritage even after the event concluded.

Policy implications

The success of the Born Farmer Cluster depended on three interlinked pillars: **skilled facilitation, access to tailored knowledge and guidance, and a common economic interest of the cluster farmers.** Evidence from the FRAMEwork project across Europe highlights how these elements can work together to drive long-term conservation outcomes.

- **Skilled facilitation is essential**

Facilitators are the linchpins of effective Farmer Clusters. They coordinate meetings, deliver training, monitor progress, and connect farmers with NGOs, researchers, and policymakers. In the Born cluster, facilitators tried to speak with farmers in their preferred language to prevent the reluctance and inhibited participation that often accompany discussions in a non-native tongue. However, due to the linguistic diversity of Luxembourg, it was not possible to fully comply with this ambition. Where **facilitation was strong and linguistically inclusive, trust and peer learning flourished**; where it was weak or language barriers remained, engagement declined. Well-resourced facilitators are vital for building cohesion, sustaining motivation, and ensuring lasting impact. Policy must prioritise **investment in facilitator training and support** (including language and communication skills) to maintain momentum and avoid fragmentation.

- **Access to knowledge, advice, and practical tools**

Farmers need more than goodwill—they need the right information at the right time. Platforms like Recodo.io provide open-access training, biodiversity monitoring protocols, and practical tools for running meetings and farm walks—sample agendas, simple sustainability assessment tools, plain-language factsheets, and outreach templates—that help both facilitators and farmers. Farmer Cluster meetings also serve as a forum for the local nature and forest administration to engage directly with farmers, presenting environmental schemes beyond the typical agro-environmental measures and customizing support to local needs. These combined tools and interactions enable the adoption of biodiversity-friendly practices and help align on-the-ground actions with broader conservation goals. To support the uptake and diffusion of these platforms, policy should fund their initial phase: make the platform accessible and regularly updated, adapt content to local contexts, and run early outreach so other farmers can find and use it. Support should also cover **plain-language editing and translation** to keep materials clear and tailored to local contexts. Finally, governmental actor participation in cluster meetings should be institutionalized to maximize outreach and impact.

- **Incentives that support voluntary, collective action**

Incentives are most effective when they respect farmers' autonomy, leverage market-based mechanisms and foster collaboration. FRAMEwork findings show that farmers consistently preferred schemes that encourage **voluntary** cooperation over those that **required** Farmer Cluster membership for eligibility. Clusters saw higher engagement when incentives **allowed flexible participation and supported peer-led initiatives**. Collective result-based payments enhanced conservation outcomes and built peer accountability. Buyer support for the fruit improved cooperation, underscoring the value of collaboration along the value chain. This support can be direct, such as fair, transparent price premiums and stable contracts for biodiversity-sensitive produce, or indirect, such as co-funding cluster coordination and organising customer-facing events (for example, tastings and farm walks) that explain the products and what sets them apart.

References / Further Reading

McHugh NM, Ness E, Holland J, Buckerfield C, Friedel J, Salehi A, Starz W, Ablinger D, Veromann E, Kaasik R, Sánchez C, Varas G, L'Hote P, Frank P, Warlop F, Bagnoni V, Marini S, Moonen C, Beyer M, Martin Y, Vray S, van Rijn P, Duijvestijn L, Bohnet I, Travnicek J, Janečková K, Banks G, Simmons A, Begg G (2022): Farmer clusters: a framework for connecting conservation measures in agricultural land. IOBC/WPRS Bulletin 156: 66-70

Regan, Á., & Kenny, U. (2022). What do the public want to know about farming and why? Sustainability, 14(9), 5391. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095391>

Tosun, J., Schaub, S., & Marek, C. (2024). Europeans' attitudes toward the goals of agricultural policy: A case of rural–urban divide? Political Studies Review, 22(1), 174–192. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14789299221149505>

Youri, M., Vray, S., Rugani, B., van Ossel Leclercq, E., Boden, J & Beyer, M. (2023). Realising agrobiodiversity management across ecosystems with farmer clusters (<https://zenodo.org/record/8402825>).

To learn more about the FRAMEwork eleven Farmer Cluster, see <https://recodo.io/page/farmer-clusters/farmer-cluster-finder>.

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Publisher(s): Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology

Author(s): Marco Beyer, Claudio Petucco

Contact: marco.beyer@list.lu

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